
STARFORD INTERNATIONAL UNIVERSITY, SOUTH SUDAN

“Education for sustainable development”

COLLEGE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE AND INFORMATION
TECHNOLOGY
DEPARTMENT OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY
AN INTERNSHIP REPORT

CONDUCTED AT MIZTECH COMPUTER SHOP AND REPAIR

BY LINO LAZAROUS MARINO IJA

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SUBMITTED IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT FOR THE
AWARD OF DIPLOMA OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

DECEMBER 2022

DECLARATION

I **Lino Lazarous Marino Ija of Reg. No: 19/SIU/DIT/3170** hereby declares that I have undertaken 8 weeks field attachment training at Miztech Computer Shop and Repair. This internship report is submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the award of diploma of information technology (Computer Science and Information Technology) at Starford International University, South Sudan. The matter presented in this internship report has not formed the basis for the award of any other degree or diploma.

Signature of the Student:

Place: Miztech Computer Shop and Repair

Date: 25-12-2022

APPROVAL

This is to certify that **Lino Lazarous Marino Ija of Reg. No: 19/SIU/DIT/3170** has conducted his field attachment training at Miztech Computer Shop and repair in Juba- South Sudan. This internship training has been conducted under my supervision, submitted in partial fulfillment for the award of diploma of Information Technology in Starford International University, South Sudan.

Signature of Academic Supervisor:

Name: Mr. Moses Marial

Date: 25-12-2022

DEDICATION

I dedicate this internship report to my parents; Pastor Lazarous Marino Ija and Mary Kaku for raising me up in the way of God. If it is not because of God's grace and love in my life. I would have not been here since there were thousands of people who passed away not because of my good works but by His grace and agape love He has towards me.

I also dedicate this internship report to my brothers, sisters, friends and brethren in Christ who always support me in prayers and advices.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

It is a great happiness and privilege for me to present this internship report. I have completed the 8 weeks of field attachment training at Miztech Computer Shop and Repair.

I would like to express my gratitude towards all those people who have in various ways helped me in compilation of my internship report successfully.

I would also like to be thankful to my work place supervisor, academic supervisor, colleagues and team members for their valuable support and corporation during my internship.

ABSTRACT

Miztech Computer Shop and Repair is located at Konyokonyo Freedom Square, Juba- South Sudan. Exist to provide software and hardware maintenance, cleaning and repairs, to improve the new and better use of technology within South Sudan and the rest of the world.

ACRONYMS/ ABBREVIATION

BIOS	Basic Input/ Output System
CD-ROM	Compact Disk- Read Only Memory
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DIT	Diploma in Information Technology
DVD	Digital Video Dics
HDD	Hard Disk Drives
IT	Information Technology
SIU	Starford International University
USB	Universal Serial Bus

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Field attachment is a policy in Starford International University, that students must do internship as part of their graduation's requirement. The specific objectives for the field attachment are to:

- Enable the students to get an opportunity of putting into practice the theoretical knowledge they learnt in lectures.
- Develop professional responsibility.
- Enhance and strengthen the linkages between Starford International University and various stakeholders.

This internship report covers four chapters with different activities, tasks, assignment and issues discussed during the field attachment training as cited below:

- Chapter one covers the information about the shop (business center), its background, and objectives.
- Chapter two covers the practical knowledge gained during the placement.
- Chapter three covers the evaluation of my performance during the placement.
- Chapter Four covers the conclusions and recommendations during the industrial's training.

The activities, tasks and assignments was for a period of 8 weeks and the internship was intended to expose me to the practical application, knowledge and skills in the field of IT.

During the 8 weeks of field attachment training, I attained more experiences and skills at Miztech Computer Shop and Repair in which I participated in number of activities like;

- Software's installation.
- Software's and Hardware's repair as well as Software's and Hardware's maintenance.

Table of Contents	Pages
<i>DECLARATION</i>	<i>i</i>
<i>APPROVAL</i>	<i>ii</i>
<i>DEDICATION</i>	<i>iii</i>
<i>ACKNOWLEDGEMENT</i>	<i>iv</i>
<i>ABSTRACT</i>	<i>v</i>
<i>ACRONYMS/ ABBREVIATION</i>	<i>vi</i>
<i>EXECUTIVE SUMMARY</i>	<i>vii</i>
CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION	1
1.0 INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 BACKGROUND OF THE FIELD ATTACHMENT	1
1.2 Objectives of the field attachment	2
1.3 Background of Miztech Computer Shop and Repair	2
1.4 Geographical location of Miztech Computer Shop and Repair	2
1.5 General activities of Miztech Computer Shop and Repair	2
1.6 Vision of Miztech Computer Shop and Repair	3
1.7 Mission of Miztech Computer Shop and Repair	3
1.8 Strategic goal and objectives of Miztech Computer Shop and Repair	3
1.9 Core values of Miztech Computer Shop and Repair	3
CHAPTER TWO: STUDENT’S EXPERIENCES	3
2.0 INTRODUCTION	3
2.1.1 Titles the interns occupied	4
2.1 DUTIES AND RESPONSIBILITIES	4
2.1.1 Attendance and orientation	4
2.1.2 Other duties and responsibilities	4
2.1.3 Supervision levels and relationship with the supervisor	4
2.1.3 Work team and its composition	5
2.1.4 Relationship among team members and other staffs	5
2.1.5 Authority level to the student	5
CHAPTER THREE: EVALUATION	6
3.0 INTRODUCTION	6
3.1 LEVEL OF ACCOMPLISHMENT OF DUTIES AND RESPONSIBILITIES ASSIGNED	6
3.2 NEW KNOWLEDGE AND SKILLS	6

3.3 SKILLS GAINED ON FIELD ATTACHMENT 6

 3.3.1 Communication skills..... 6

 3.3.2 Team work skills 6

 3.3.3 Software installation’s skills 6

 3.3.4 Maintenance, troubleshooting and repair skills..... 7

 3.3.5 Computer maintenance skills 8

 3.3.6 Disassembling and assembling CPU skills 9

3.4 LESSONS LEARNT..... 9

3.5 MOST INTERESTING EXPERIENCES ATTAINED 9

3.6 RELATION OF KNOWLEDGE TAUGHT IN UNIVERSITY AND FIELD ATTACHMENT..... 10

3.7 CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS ENCOUNTERED 10

3.8 WAY FORWARD FOR THE CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED 10

CHAPTER FOUR: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS..... 11

 4.1 CONCLUSIONS..... 11

 4.1.1 Strengths 11

 4.1.2 Weakness..... 11

 4.2 RECOMMENDATIONS 11

 4.2.1 Recommendations for the university 11

 4.2.2 Recommendations for companies, Organizations, Business centers, etc. 11

 4.2.3 Recommendations for the students..... 12

REFERENCES..... 13

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Field's attachment training is one of the requirement of graduation in Starford International University. The training carried out is to equip the students with work place skills.

This field attachment report was the result of activities, tasks and assignment conducted at Miztech Computer Shop and Repair which was scheduled for the period of 8 weeks.

Students and graduates looking to gain relevant skills and experience in a particular field typically undertake them (Douglas and Adam, 2017). The field attachment report is a formal document that illustrates the trainings, skills attained and activities done by the intern while at his/ her internship work place. This report is meant to cover the information about the background of the shop (business center), the main activities of the business center, the vision, mission, and core values all in the first chapter.

Other chapters cover the information about the task, experiences and skills attained by the intern during the field attachment period. The challenges faced by intern and the way of managing the challenges.

The last chapter covers the conclusions and recommendations suggested for the Universities, students, and companies, organizations or business centers.

1.1 BACKGROUND OF THE FIELD ATTACHMENT

- This industrial's training has been the realization that imparts the relevant practical skills and experiences.
- It also develops partnership between the training institutions and Universities.
- Field attachment is one of the requirements for graduation in Starford International University, South Sudan.

1.2 Objectives of the field attachment

The specific objectives for the field attachment are to:

- Enable students to get an opportunity of putting into practice the theoretical knowledge they learn in lectures.
- Develop professional responsibility and skills on their field of specialization.
- Enhance and strengthen linkages between Starford international university and various stakeholders.

1.3 Background of Miztech Computer Shop and Repair

Miztech Computer shop and Repair is a registered shop in Juba- South Sudan. It provide software and hardware maintenance, cleaning and repairs, to improve the new and better use of technology within South Sudan and the rest of the world.

1.4 Geographical location of Miztech Computer Shop and Repair

Miztech Computer Shop and Repair is located at Konyokonyo freedom Square, 1st floor Room 17 in Juba- South Sudan.

1.5 General activities of Miztech Computer Shop and Repair

- Computer repair and maintenance.
- Selling spare parts for the computer.
- Training interns to gained computer skills.
- Repairing and maintaining printers.
- Setting up networks for businesses centers, and homes.
- Software's installation.
- Software's and Hardware's repair as well as Software's and Hardware's maintenance.

1.6 Vision of Miztech Computer Shop and Repair

To be a leading technological center in Juba and abroad.

1.7 Mission of Miztech Computer Shop and Repair

- To maintain machines for both students and staffs including home's machines.
- To reduce high cost of technology by providing repairs, maintenance and troubleshooting machines.
- To improve better use of technology within South Sudan and the rest of the world.

1.8 Strategic goal and objectives of Miztech Computer Shop and Repair

The strategic goal is to aim higher in technology and the strategic objective is to provide quality services to the clients.

1.9 Core values of Miztech Computer Shop and Repair

- Team work
- Transparency in work
- Quality provision of services

CHAPTER TWO: STUDENT'S EXPERIENCES

2.0 INTRODUCTION

This chapter explain the details of training and tasks on the field attachment at Miztech Computer Shop and Repair. The training is to impact the interns on how to apply the theoretical knowledge they learnt in lectures into practice in order for the interns to attain working experiences and to gain practical skills.

2.1.1 Titles the interns occupied

The interns are not given any titles since they are yet pursuing their programs and are not staffs. The interns are for a limited period of time in organizations, companies, government institutions, and business centers as required by the university's administration.

2.1 DUTIES AND RESPONSIBILITIES

2.1.1 Attendance and orientation

The intern was introduced to the staffs of Miztech Computer Shop and Repair and was briefed on dos and don'ts.

2.1.2 Other duties and responsibilities

- I was responsible for the other duties and responsibilities such as; Computer Care, troubleshooting, repair and Maintenance.
- Working with different technicians on machines' repair.
- Assisting technicians with relevant tasks.
- Testing new machines like chargers, flasks disks and etc.
- Doing other assignments given to the intern by the technician.

2.1.3 Supervision levels and relationship with the supervisor

I was placed in the department of Information Technology specifically on computer repair and maintenance. During my supervision, while at Miztech Computer Shop and Repair by my work place supervisor Mr. Simon, I was directed wherever necessary.

My academic supervisor Mr. Moses Marial from the University checked on me during the field attachment at Miztech Computer Shop and Repair and he guided me on how to write this report.

The academic supervisor interacted with the field supervisors about my performance in the work place.

2.1.3 Work team and its composition

Miztech Computer Shop and Repair cannot separate both the interns and staffs. They accept interns and staffs from different nationality and universities.

2.1.4 Relationship among team members and other staffs

The interns and staffs are always working together hand-in-hand with one another. While I was at Miztech Computer Shop and Repair there was cooperation, team work and transparency between the staffs and interns even with clients and other members who comes from other organizations, companies and government institutions.

2.1.5 Authority level to the student

I have minimum authority since I have no any other title only the intern. Administration of the business center gives me access to all the tools of the shop to use them where necessary. And I was given right to converse with the clients.

I was permitted to ask anything I didn't know and to allow my academic supervisor to pay visit to my internship placement.

CHAPTER THREE: EVALUATION

3.0 INTRODUCTION

This chapter is going to highlights the experiences and skills attained. The knowledge gained and the challenges and limitations that could not allow other activities to be possible.

3.1 LEVEL OF ACCOMPLISHMENT OF DUTIES AND RESPONSIBILITIES ASSIGNED

I was able to perform and accomplish all the duties assigned to me though there were some few challenges and limitations; I managed to cover most of the part.

3.2 NEW KNOWLEDGE AND SKILLS

I able to acquired new knowledge and skills during the field attachment. In which practical skills and work place experiences are the great achievements for me.

3.3 SKILLS GAINED ON FIELD ATTACHMENT

3.3.1 Communication skills

I was able to enhance and strengthen my communication skills since I interact with clients and staffs at large. And there is a great change on my communication skills like never before, on how to talk to clients and staffs in polite, calm, and good way.

3.3.2 Team work skills

I have been given a number of activities and tasks to share with others in which it needs some of their guidance and indeed they directed me resulting to easy accomplishment of activities.

3.3.3 Software installation's skills

I was assigned to installs both systems and applications software and also to diagnose the problems that were encountered during installation, for both system and application software.

Some of the applications I installed were: Installation of antivirus software (Kaspersky Anti-virus of different versions) and updating it, Installation of Operating system (Windows 7, 10 and 11), Installation of Microsoft Office application program, Installation of Micro Dynamics NAV, Installation of outlook and its configurations, Installing Browsers (Firefox, Chrome) and configuring it.

3.3.4 Maintenance, troubleshooting and repair skills

This is to keep computers in good condition, by maintaining, troubleshooting and repairing them. If the computers are not well maintained, they can easily fall prey to problems caused by heat, dust, viruses, misuse and fluctuating electrical supplies.

Basic Computer Hardware Components

Hardware is the physical equipment needed for a computer to function properly.

The basic hardware parts I learned were:

Case: is the box that encloses many of the parts of the computer. It has attachment points, slots and screws that allow parts of the system to be fitted onto the case.

Power Supply: used to connect all of the parts of the computer described to electrical power.

Fan: needed to disperse the significant amount of heat that is generated by the electrically powered parts in a computer.

Motherboard: is a large electronic board that is used to connect the power supply to various other electronic parts and to hold the parts in place on the computer. The computer's memory and processor are attached to the motherboard. Also found on the motherboard are the BIOS chip that is responsible for some fundamental operations of the computer, such as linking hardware and

software. The motherboard also contains a small battery and the chips that work with it to store the system time and some other computer settings.

Drives: Are the devices used for long term storage of information. The main storage area for a computer is its internal hard drive (also called hard disk drives (HDD)).

Floppy disk drive: was very common until recent years, and is still found on many older desktop computers. It was replaced by USB, CD-ROM and DVD drives, which have higher storage capacities.

3.3.5 Computer maintenance skills

Computer maintenance refers to operational and functional checks, servicing, repairing, replacing if necessary devices and supporting utilities. The kinds of maintenance I have learnt are:

Conditional-base maintenance: is performed after one or more indicators show that the device is going to fail or that Hardware's or software's performance is deteriorating.

Corrective maintenance: I have learnt how to identify, isolate and rectify a fault parts in a system so that the failed software or hardware system can be restored to an operational condition within the tolerances or limits established for in-service operations.

Planned preventive maintenance: I have learnt how to scheduled service visit carried out by the competent and suitable agent to ensure that the device is operating correctly and to avoid any unscheduled Breakdown and downtime

Predictive maintenance: I have learnt the techniques that are designed to help determine the condition of in-service device in order to predict when maintenance should be performed.

Preventive maintenance: I have learnt how to follow the planned guidelines from time-to-time to prevent the breakdown of machines.

Total productive maintenance: I have learnt how to maintain and improve the integrity of production and quality systems through the computers that add business value to a shop.

3.3.6 Disassembling and assembling CPU skills

I have learnt how to disassemble and assemble a system unit. The following are some of the steps in case you want to replace a motherboard:

- Disconnecting all cables and removing all expansion cards from the old motherboard.
- Removing the screws that secure the old motherboard and remove the old motherboard.
- Removing and installing the new motherboard mounting posts as necessary to match the mounting holes on the motherboard.
- Install the new motherboard and secure it with screws in all mounting whole positions.
- Reinstall all the expansion cards and reconnect the cables.

3.4 LESSONS LEARNT

- I have learnt how to repair computers.
- I have learnt how to maintain the computers.
- I have learnt how to installs software and restoration of cracked software.
- I have learnt how to work as a team.

3.5 MOST INTERESTING EXPERIENCES ATTAINED

- I have gained knowledge on computer repair and maintenance. In which I was taught how to repair, maintain, and service laptops and system Unit.
- I also learnt how to clean different types of machines.
- I learnt how to replace faulty parts of laptops and system Unit.
- I learnt how to manage and keep time.
- Also to speak with confidence to the staffs.

3.6 RELATION OF KNOWLEDGE TAUGHT IN UNIVERSITY AND FIELD ATTACHMENT

- I have learnt the practical skills of the theoretical knowledge I learnt in the lectures.
- I was exposed to various stakeholders through the skills I learnt during my field attachment.

3.7 CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS ENCOUNTERED

High expenses: transport and lunch fare were high because the internship center was far and I have to provide for myself.

Short period of field attachment: the period given for the field attachment was limited to learn the practical skills of the theoretical knowledge learnt in lectures for the period of either 3 or 4 years.

3.8 WAY FORWARD FOR THE CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED

- If possible the companies, business centers, governmental organizations, or organizations should at least provide transport fare for the interns.
- The University should at least increase the field attachment period to 4 months.
- The University should allocate the academic supervisors as early as possible.

CHAPTER FOUR: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1 CONCLUSIONS

I would like to appreciate Starford International University for sending me into field attachment to gain practical skills of what I have been learning for the period of three years.

I also appreciate Miztech Computer Shop and Repair for accepting me in order to attain knowledge and skills in the field of IT specifically computer repair and maintenance both software and hardware repair and maintenance.

4.1.1 Strengths

I now had a wide range of Computer skill, how to repair and maintain computers. The field attachment had helped me much to apply my theoretical knowledge into a practical skills.

The field supervisor took time to offer me the skills as much as he can. In which I attained new technological knowledge and work place skills.

4.1.2 Weakness

The field attachment period is too short in which I acquired less knowledge than if it could be for four months or more.

4.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

4.2.1 Recommendations for the university

The University's administration should extend the field attachment period to at least four months for the students to have enough time for learning and compiling of report in time.

4.2.2 Recommendations for companies, Organizations, Business centers, etc.

If possible, the organization should at least provide either transportation or lunch fare to the interns in order for the interns to be more actively and come early during their internship period.

4.2.3 Recommendations for the students

- The Students should apply what they have learnt into practice as an opportunity to enhance and strengthen their practical skills and work place skills.
- The students should at least ask as much questions as possible at their internship placement to improve on their professional experiences and skills.

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